

Additional information 1: The location of the provinces in The Netherlands: Friesland (FR), Groningen (GR), Flevoland (FL), Utrecht (UT), Drenthe (DR), Overijssel (OV), Gelderland (GD), Noord-Brabant (NB), Limburg (LB), Zeeland (ZL), Zuid-Holland (ZH) and Noord-Holland (NH).

Additional information 2: NCBI isolates used in the sequence comparisons per virus and per ORF.

BMV	Nr of NCBI isolates	NCBI isolates used
ORF0	21	X83110, NC_003491, KC121026, MW367423, DQ132996, EF107543, EU022479, EU022483, EU022484, EU022487, EU022488, EU022486, EU022478, EU022476, EU022474, EU022473, EU022475, EU022482, EU022485, EU022480, EU022481
ORF1	6	X83110, NC_003491, KC121026, MW367423, DQ132996, EF107543
ORF1-2	6	X83110, NC_003491, KC121026, MW367423, DQ132996, EF107543
ORF3	9	X83110, NC_003491, KC121026, MW367423, DQ132996, EF107543, EU148509, EU148510, EU148508
ORF3a	6	X83110, NC_003491, KC121026, MW367423, DQ132996, EF107543
ORF3-5	9	X83110, NC_003491, KC121026, MW367423, DQ132996, EF107543, EU148509, EU148510, EU148508
ORF4	22	X83110, NC_003491, KC121026, MW367423, DQ132996, EF107543, EU148509, EU148510, EU148508, EU022504, EU022507, EU022502, EU022499, EU022500, EU022498, EU022501, EU022496, EU022503, EU022506, EU022497, GU002354, FN827048

BChV	Nr of NCBI isolates	NCBI isolates used
ORF0	21	AF352024, NC_002766, MH271171, MW367424, AF352025, MN734427, AF168610, AF168607, AF168609, EU022477, EF659974, EU022472, EU022469, EU022471, EU022465, EU022464, EU022466, EU022467, EU022468, AF168605, EU022470
ORF1	6	AF352024, NC_002766, MH271171, MW367424, AF352025, MN734427
ORF1-2	6	AF352024, NC_002766, MH271171, MW367424, AF352025, MN734427
ORF3	9	AF352024, NC_002766, MH271171, MW367424, AF352025, MN734427, EU022510, EU022511, EU022509
ORF3a	6	AF352024, NC_002766, MH271171, MW367424, AF352025, MN734427
ORF3-5	9	AF352024, NC_002766, MH271171, MW367424, EU022510, EU022511, EU022509, MN734427, AF352025
ORF4	21	AF352024, NC_002766, MH271171, MW367424, AF352025, MN734427, EU022510, EU022511, EU022509, EF659975, AF167475, AF167483, AF167485, EU022495, AF167476, EU022490, EU022491, EU022492, EU022493, EU022494, JX465678

BYV	Nr of NCBI isolates	Dutch isolates only
ORF1a	7	MW274719, MT701720, MT815988, AF056575, AF190581, X73476, NC_001598
ORF1a/b	7	MW274719, MT701720, MT815988, AF056575, AF190581, X73476, NC_001598
ORF2	9	MW274719, MT701720, MT815988, AF056575, AF190581, X73476, NC_001598, X53462, X73475

ORF3	19	MW274719, MT701720, MT815988, AF056575, AF190581, X73476, NC_001598, X53462, X73475
ORF4	9	MW274719, MT701720, MT815988, AF056575, AF190581, X73476, NC_001598, X53462, X73475
ORF5	11	MW274719, MT701720, MT815988, AF056575, AF190581, X73476, NC_001598, X53462, X73475, BYVVCPG, BYU71437
ORF6	10	MW274719, MT701720, MT815988, AF056575, AF190581, X73476, NC_001598, X53462, X73475, BYVVCPG
ORF7	11	MW274719, MT701720, MT815988, AF056575, AF190581, X73476, NC_001598, X53462, X73475, FJ711759, BYU71296
ORF8	8	MW274719, MT701720, MT815988, AF056575, AF190581, X73476, NC_001598, X53462

Additional information 3: The details of the Dutch field isolates used for sequencing; name, virus species and year and place of collection

Name isolate	Virus	Province	City	Year
BMVYV_GR	BMVYV	GR	Scheemda	2019
BMVYV_DR	BMVYV	DR	Nieuw Amsterdam	2019
BMVYV_ZL_1	BMVYV	ZL	Zoutelande	2019
BMVYV_ZL_2	BMVYV	ZL	Biggekerke	2019
BMVYV_ZL_3	BMVYV	ZL	Aagtekerke	2019
BMVYV_ZL_4	BMVYV	ZL	Kloosterzande	2019
BChV_ZL	BChV	ZL	Wilhelminadorp	2019
BChV_NH	BChV	NH	Wieringerwerf	2021
BChV_FR	BChV	FR	Lauwersmeer	2022
BYV_GR_1	BYV	GR	Uithuizermeeden	2019
BYV_GR_2	BYV	GR	Oudeschip	2019
BYV_GR_3	BYV	GR	Warffum	2020
BYV_NB_1	BYV	NB	Westerbeek	2020
BYV_NB_2	BYV	NB	Deurne	2019
BYV_FL	BYV	FL	Dronten	2020
BYV_LB	BYV	LB	Doenrade	2019
BYV_ZH	BYV	ZH	Strijen	2020